

Neutrosophy-Driven Deep Learning for Predicting Student Performance

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Abstract: This paper proposes a hybrid architecture using several deep learning models in the neutrosophy environment for predicting student learning outcomes. The proposed framework proceeds on deep neural network models with the neutrosophy encoder/decoder. The experimental results on the actual data of the Hanoi Metropolitan University show that the proposed model's RMSE, MAE, and R2 metrics are better than the deterministic models. Especially, when using the previous 3 semesters for the prediction model, the R2-score of all 05 proposed frameworks are approximately 60%, which proves the suitability of the proposed approach for the educational data and the prediction student outcomes problem.

Keywords: Neutrosophy; Prediction student outcomes; DNN; CNN; RNN; LSTM; Transformer.

1. Introduction

Recent advancements in educational technology have led to an exponential growth in online educational data sources, providing a vast archive of educational data and the effective data mining tools [24,39,70,71]. This unprecedented rise in educational data has created an opportunity to optimize user engagement with technology platforms, thereby enhancing the learning experience (Shorfuzzaman et al., 2019; Jarbou et al., 2023; Zhang, 2023)[26,48,70]. This surge in cumulative educational data has also spurred the emergence of new research trends, such as the use of educational data analysis to predict learner behavior and inform education policy formulation by managers [28,39,52]. Analytics in educational data, which is the product of learner-teacher interaction, has evolved into a multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary field of research, involving scholars from diverse research backgrounds [64]. Data science in education refers to the close collaboration of researchers from different fields and backgrounds, who work collaboratively to address research concerns related to educational data.

In universities, many students have difficulty completing courses because of the lack of support and direction needed in some complex courses, thereby depriving

students of motivation to study and it may be the cause of student dropout [3,69]. Predicting student learning outcomes is one of the solutions that help to monitor students' learning process, orient development, and improve students' learning ability based on predictive results, thereby helping students improve their learning efficiency and increase student retention [8,35]. However, up to now, the studies aimed at applying the learning prediction results of students in counseling and supporting their learning orientation have not been focused. In other words, it is not commensurate with the development trend of digital universities in this digital era.

It is a fact that as the data warehouse of human knowledge increases, the ambiguous information in it also increases resonance, because that is one of the natural characteristics of data. Smarandache [50,51], an American computer science professor, proposed to construct a new logical structure – Neutrosophic Logic, a true extension of the classical fuzzy logic, allowing consideration of the ambiguity information in the educational data. In Neutrosophic logic, one can deal with data containing statements that are not solely true or false, but also but neutral, indeterminate or somewhere in between. The neutrosophic part, the indeterminacy part, are inherent in every field, where it gives rise to research topics such as neutrosophic decision making [66,67], management and communication network [58] granular and stochastic computing [53,54], etc. Recently, research on Neutrosophic logic has continued to expand with wide-ranging applications across various fields. In multi-criteria decision-making, advanced methods such as Neutrosophic VIKOR and integrated models with evidence theory have been proposed to address uncertainty and mixed-type data, particularly in areas such as hospital planning and information quality assessment [27,36,44]. In the realm of stochastic computing, Granados and Valencia Henao (2024) introduced a refined Neutrosophic stochastic process, establishing a theoretical foundation for probabilistic computation under uncertainty [17]. In the fields of pattern recognition (Sahin et al., 2017) and group decision-making, linguistic and multivalued Neutrosophic aggregation operators have also been extended to enhance decision accuracy in ambiguous contexts [13]. Moreover, the 2024 MeCoNeT Conference highlights the increasing academic interest in Neutrosophic theory at the global level [32].

In the education environment, the assessment of students always has uncertainty and inconsistency. For example, the use of regular assessment scores in the process of converting points (attendance assessment, interaction assessment, questions and answers, mid-term assessment, end-of-term evaluation, etc). The performance grade can be given in the form of assignments or task scores, project implementation; presentation scores, major exercise scores, question and answer scores, etc. It deeply depends on each context and the purpose of the education system, even the enthusiasm of the educator, teachers and many other factors [6,19,42]. In addition, online teaching in recent years has gradually become an indispensable companion in the educational

process, especially during the Covid-19 epidemic. Different forms of teaching lead to different assessment methods and different levels of scoring with different scales. For example, subject scores can be shown through online interaction, through the number of clicks or through the performance of the action according to the instructor's instructions, etc. The method used to convert points from letter points to scores and vice versa, how to calculate the average score, and the rules for classifying students according to levels (excellent, good, decent, average, weak, poor) also contain certain factors of error and uncertainty for each type of conversion, leading to ambiguous and inaccurate information. In addition, it is necessary to mention factors affecting students' learning outcomes such as learning methods, assessment methods/difficulty of assessment tests; subject/difficulty level of the subject; lecturer/lecturer's assessment method; psychological state of students, etc. These factors directly affect learners' scores, and it is necessary to include in the predictive model quantities that represent the model's uncertainties. In an attempt to reduce the uncertainty in the students' assessment process, several attempts have been made in the last decade to use fuzzy set theory in educational evaluation [5,19,20,21,47,60,62]. Therefore, researching the uncertainty theory (such as fuzzy theory, and neutrosophic theory) dealing with machine learning models, and deep learning models in forecasting problems is very necessary [11,57], especially related to education data.

The main problem of this paper is to predict the student's outcome based on some given in-complete educational datasets. With approach acknowledges that educational data can contain ambiguous and inaccurate information due to factors such as conversion methods, assessment difficulty, learning methods, and psychological states of students, this paper propose to incorporate neutrosophic logic and uncertainty theory into the proposed model to represent both the prediction results and their indeterminacies. In particular, neutrosophic theory is combined with deep learning models to create a framework for predicting student 's outcomes. The data is processed using neutrosophic functions, which represent the uncertainty and indeterminacy of the data sets. This allows the model to capture and account for the inherent uncertainties and inconsistencies in the educational data, leading to more accurate predictions. In fact, the uncertainty of a data sample will be described through a vector with attributes of significance in neutrosophicization. To show the effectiveness of the proposed method, the neutrosophic coherence models were compared with conventional models on experimental datasets collected from Hanoi Metropolitan University (HNMU), Hanoi, Vietnam with 2613 observations of students in Primary Education major with 85 attribute variables. The data was redistributed by time scale, sorted by semesters, and labeled data samples were used for training and testing. We parallelly designed prediction problems with different scenarios:

- (1) Using the previous semester's average data to predict the next semester's average score;

- (2) Using the average data of the 2 previous semesters to predict the average score of the third semester;
- (3) Using the average data of the 3 previous semesters to predict the average score of the fourth semester, and go on, etc.

By using some deep learning methods such as DNN (Deep Neural Networks), CNN (Convolutional Neural Networks), RNN (Recurrent Neural Networks), LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory Networks) and Transformer combined with neutrosophic input data, the proposed method achieves an average error of RMSE; MAE and R2 in the neutrosophic data with the 3rd scenario are better than the second and the first, and of course are better than that of real data. It means that the proposed method has a stronger effect on the combined data dealing with noise as fuzzification by neutrosophic functions.

The main contribution of this paper is to propose some combination models based on deep learning models (DNN, CNN, RNN, LSTM, and Transformer) with neutrosophic encoder/decoder modules to predict student learning outcomes. The student's semester averages are used as input, and trapezoidal neutrosophic functions are fed into the models that represent the uncertainties of the data. For an input data sample, we include up to 6 neutrosophic functional factors:

Very Poor ($T_{Very\ Poor}, I_{Very\ Poor}, F_{Very\ Poor}$),

Poor ($T_{Poor}, I_{Poor}, F_{Poor}$),

Fair ($T_{Fair}, I_{Fair}, F_{Fair}$),

Good ($T_{Good}, I_{Good}, F_{Good}$),

Very Good ($T_{Very\ Good}, I_{Very\ Good}, F_{Very\ Good}$),

Excellent ($T_{Excellent}, I_{Excellent}, F_{Excellent}$).

Comparing the accuracy of the prediction problem according to RMSE, MSE, and R2 metrics with the real cases; we can make judgments about the advantages and disadvantages, as well as the superiority of the models used. In particular, the proposed method is concretized in the goal of predicting students at risk of failing, to give early warnings to students and managers to take timely remedial measures. On that basis, the learner-oriented consultant can make early adjustments if necessary to achieve the desired learning results, and the educational administrator can rank and create a source of excellent students for new fields of study, etc.

The paper has been structured as follows. Section 2 briefly describes some related documents with the research topic. Section 3 presents the neutrosophic set, neutrosophic number and recalls the basics of deep learning models: DNN, CNN, RNN, LSTM and Transformer. The problem and the model of deep learning combined with

neutrosophic theory are detailed in Section 4. In Section 5, the experimental results on the dataset of HNMU are given along with the scientific conclusions achieved. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper and discusses potential directions of further studies.

2. Literature review

We live in the era of big data, where all sectors generate an incredible amount of data. This has created unprecedented challenges for data analysis. As a result, there is an urgent need for machine learning, deep learning, and artificial intelligence applications to analyze these more and more complicated data [30,31,33,34].

Although artificial neural networks have been used since the 1950s [40], it was not until 2006 that the field of deep learning (DL) was established [22]. Since then, DL has gained considerable attention from scientists and engineers due to its ability to create complex predictive models using a range of learning algorithms. These algorithms include multi-layer neural networks with numerous hidden nodes [29], convolutional neural networks (CNNs), and regional CNNs [15,16], among others. Many of these supervised and unsupervised DL models are characterized by the presence of numerous hidden layers of neurons that facilitate the learning process. Deep Neural Networks (DNN), CNNs, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTMs), and Transformers are some of the popular DL methods that form the core architecture of current deep learning models and are invaluable tools for data scientists. Wide applications of these methods in real problems have been studied in recent years such as the problem of reducing the consumption of household systems [31], or the solution for preventing the illegal disposal of waste in smart cities [30], etc.

Rapid advances in advanced learning technology platforms have increased online education data sources with rich educational data repositories. This rapid increase in educational data also provides opportunities to optimize user engagement with technology platforms to enhance learning experiences [48]. The growth of accumulated educational data has stimulated the emergence of several new research trends, such as analyzing educational data to predict learner behavior and provide indicators for educational policy development [7,59]. Educational data analysis includes several aspects: collecting, aggregating, examining, and analyzing information of learners and teachers to improve understanding of the learning environment, leading to student learning outcomes and teacher performance being optimized. This field emphasizes the assessment of individual student achievement and the corresponding impact of individual achievement on the performance of educational institutions. In addition, education data analysis deals with formulating policies and developing strategies to enhance the management capacity of educational institutions by making effective decisions. There have been many studies using educational data mining methods, such as Decision Trees, KNN, Bayes, Association rules, Logistic Regression, etc., to solve the problem of predicting learning outcomes and the capacity of learners and bring many positive results [49,56,65]. Zafar Iqbal and his colleagues studied real datasets mined from Information Technology University (ITU), Lahore, Pakistan, to

make predictions for student learning outcomes. In their work [69], the authors analyzed the data of the entrance scores of ITU students to predict the learning outcomes for first-year students and also pointed out the important factors in the process of predicting student performance. Continuing this approach, Zafar Iqbal et al. [69] have used machine learning techniques (CF, SVD, NMF, and RBM) to analyze the data of students of the Electronic Engineering department during their study at ITU, thereby giving suggestions on improving grades or pointing out students who need support, especially in courses. Alshantqi et al. showed the effectiveness of student performance prediction by combining collaborative filtering, fuzzy set rules, and Lasso linear regression [2].

Several studies have explored the use of machine learning techniques to analyze student behavior and predict students who are at risk of failing exams [55]. For instance, Waheed et al. (2019), Wasif et al. (2019), and Elbadrawy et al. (2016) have presented various methods to build predictive models using linear regression and matrix decomposition techniques [12,61,63]. The data used in these studies were generated from different universities, including George Mason University, University of Minnesota, and Stanford University MOOC. However, the matrix decomposition method has a fundamental limitation in ignoring the sequence of subjects taken by students. In another study, Iam-On and Boongoen (2017) proposed a data transformation model based on summary data matrices to classify students at Mae Fah Luang University in Thailand [25]. By using the clustering approach of data mining to generate a descriptive model from educational data, they have pointed out the prediction of student dropout. Son et al. used logistic regression and machine learning techniques to process training data from Hanoi Metropolitan University between 2016 and 2020 [52]. Their analysis and evaluation of student learning outcomes were based on admission data, as well as academic performance data from the first and second years, and pointed out the most important subject of admission that positive effect on student performance at the University. Okubo et al. (2017) used a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) to predict student grades [35]. However, the study was limited by its focus on a single course with only 108 students, which limits the generalizability of the findings. Similarly, Corrigan and Smeaton (2017) employed Random Forest, RNN, and simple LSTM to predict student success within a virtual learning environment [9]. Their findings revealed that RNN outperformed the other algorithms. Waheed et al. (2019) used deep neural networks to analyze learner interaction data and predict students at risk of failure, providing early intervention opportunities [61]. The study found that deep artificial neural networks (ANN) outperformed logistic regression and SVM models.

Additionally, recent studies [4,18,43] showcase the increasing application of machine learning algorithms to student data. These models play a vital role in refining predictions and providing valuable insights to educational institutions, enabling them to implement timely interventions. For instance, Sapkota et al. (2025) utilized XGBoost and Random Forest models to predict student graduation rates, while Halat et al. (2023)

focused on health science students' data to monitor their academic progression [18,43].

The findings from these studies suggest that deep learning models, such as BiLSTM [68], are highly effective in predicting student success, particularly in online learning environments. However, challenges remain, such as the dependence of model accuracy on the quality and quantity of the data used for training. Table 1 summarizes some literatures related to the direction of this paper.

Table 1: Results of student performance prediction using machine learning and deep learning techniques

Study	Purpose	Dataset	Method	Results
Thai-Nghe, Horváth, & Schmidt-Thieme, 2011	To predict student performance in a course	2 datasets from KDD Cup 2010	MF (Matrix Factorization Model)	Tensor-based factorization can be useful for predicting student performance
Zafar Iqbal, 2016	To predict learning outcomes for first-year students	225 data from ITU	Data analysis	Higher Secondary School Certificate performance and entry test performance are the most significant factors
Elbadrawy et al., 2016	To predict next term grade	30,754 data from GMU, 14,505 from UMN, 13,130 from SU	Personalized Multi-Linear Regression Models (PLMR)	PLMR predicts next term grade with low error
Xu, 2017	To predict student performance	1,169 data from UCLA	Latent Factor Method	Latent factor method outperforms benchmark approaches
Iam-On & Boongoen, 2017	To predict student dropout	811 data from MFLU	Data Mining, Clustering Approach	Using clustering approach to generate a descriptive model from educational data
Okubo et al., 2017	To predict student grades	108 students	RNN	Using 6 weeks of log data, accuracy was above 90%
Corrigan & Smeaton, 2017	To explore how student interactions with virtual learning environments can predict performance	2,879 data from VLE	Random Forest, RNN, simple LSTM	RNN outperforms all other algorithms
Waheed et al., 2019	To predict at-risk students	OULA dataset (32,593 students over 9 months)	ANN	Deep ANN outperforms logistic regression and SVM models

Hassan et al., 2019	To identify early withdrawals	10,140 data from India	LSTM	95.34% accuracy
Zafar Iqbal, 2021	To predict and identify students who need support	225 data from ITU	CF, SVD, NMF, RBM	RBM technique was found to be better than other techniques
Nguyen Thi Kim Son et al., 2022	To predict students' learning outcomes based on admission data	2,763 data from HNMU	Logistic Regression, Discriminative Factor Selection Technique	RMSE superior to logistic regression
Korchi et al., 2023	To predict student performance in a curriculum or program	Student dataset comprising personal information and grades	Decision Tree, Random Forest, Linear Regression, K-Nearest Neighbor, XGBoost, Deep Neural Network	Deep neural network outperformed others with a determination coefficient of 99.97%
Junru Ren, Shaomin Wu, 2023	To predict results related to dropout rates or online learning habits and performances	MOOC interaction dataset	STM, RMTTP, ERPP	MTTP applicability and effectiveness of RMTTP and ERPP models compared with traditional LSTM networks
Halat et al., 2023	To predict academic performance at Qatar University	Medical and health science student data	XGBoost	XGBoost provided the most accurate results in predicting academic performance
Yousafzai et al., 2024	To predict academic performance from behavioral data	MOOC logs (video, quiz, forum)	BiLSTM	Accuracy = 90.16%; effective but dependent on large amounts of data
Sapkota et al., 2025	To predict graduation and dropout rates of students	Student data from Qatar University	XGBoost, Random Forest, AdaBoost	XGBoost model achieved 92% accuracy, outperforming other models
Politeknik Negeri Lampung et al., 2025	To predict student graduation outcomes	6,607 samples from attendance, study hours, and parental involvement	Linear Regression, Logistic Regression	MSE = 3.256 for exam scores; graduation classification accuracy reached 99.85%

Summarisation and Research gap analysis:

Overall, the application of machine learning and deep learning to analyze educational data is still in its early stages. One of the primary reasons is that the available sources of digitized education data, while increasing, are still relatively limited

compared to other data sources like photo or ImageNet. In particular, these datasets derived from the real world also encompasses information pertaining to uncertainty, indeterminacy, and inconsistency. Additionally, there is a diverse range of data mining algorithms, machine learning techniques, and deep learning models that can be applied to these problems. Nevertheless, there exists a notable deficiency in thorough evaluative studies concerning the implementation of neutrosophic theory in conjunction with deep learning techniques to address these problems. Choosing the appropriate predictive model or deep learning technique that aligns with the logic, assessment requirements, and goals of the analysts and managers is a matter that needs to be further explored in neutrosophic environments. Furthermore, the mathematical and computational methodologies underlying deep learning modeling can be challenging to understand, especially for interdisciplinary scientists, which can pose initial difficulties in approaching this research direction. Therefore, the paper aims to propose some combination models based on deep learning models with neutrosophic encoder/decoder modules to predict student learning outcomes

3. Preliminaries

3.1. Neutrosophy

Neutrosophy is a theory that deals with the representation and analysis of indeterminacy, uncertainty, and inconsistency in various fields, including deep learning models. In the context of predicting student outcomes, neutrosophy is used to handle the inherent uncertainties and inconsistencies in educational data. Neutrosophic logic, which is an extension of classical fuzzy logic, allows for the consideration of ambiguous information in educational data. It deals with data containing statements that are not solely true or false but also neutral, indeterminate, or somewhere in between (Smarandache, 1998). The uncertainty presented here, (i.e., the indeterminacy factor) is independent of the truth and falsity values. To define a set A as a neutrosophic set (NS) in the universal X , denoted by the form $A = \{(x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x)) : x \in X\}$. In which, the degree of confidence is presented via membership function $T_A: X \rightarrow [0; 1]$; $I_A: X \rightarrow [0; 1]$ represents the indeterminacy membership function representing the degree of uncertainty, and $F_A: X \rightarrow [0; 1]$ represents the falsity membership function representing the degree of scepticism. It is required that $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3$, for all $x \in X$, ensuring that the sum of the membership values is within the valid range. In the context of the proposed framework, the neutrosophic encoder/decoder module involves the application of neutrosophic logic principles to transform and process the input and output data of the deep learning models.

In this paper, neutrosophic theory is combined with deep learning models such as DNNs, CNNs, RNNs, LSTMs, and Transformers to create a framework for predicting student outcomes. The data is processed using neutrosophic functions, which represent the uncertainty and indeterminacy of the data sets. Concretely, the single

valued trapezoidal neutrosophic functions, $[a, b, c, d; T_N, I_N, F_N]$, $a \leq b \leq c \leq d$; $0 \leq T_N, I_N, F_N \leq 1$ in the general formula, with membership functions

$$T(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq a, x > d \\ (x - a)T_N/b - a & \text{if } a < x \leq b \\ T_N & \text{if } b < x \leq c \\ (d - x)T_N/d - c & \text{if } c < x \leq d; \end{cases}$$

$$I(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \leq a, x > d \\ (b - x + (x - a)I_N)/b - a & \text{if } a < x \leq b \\ I_N & \text{if } b < x \leq c \\ (x - c + (d - x)I_N)/d - c & \text{if } c < x \leq d; \end{cases}$$

$$F(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \leq a, x > d \\ (b - x + (x - a)F_N)/b - a & \text{if } a < x \leq b \\ F_N & \text{if } b < x \leq c \\ (x - c + (d - x)F_N)/d - c & \text{if } c < x \leq d, \end{cases}$$

$x \in R$, are used in this context, where T_N, I_N, F_N are the truth degree, the indeterminacy degree, and the falsity degree, respectively. This allows the model to capture and account for the inherent uncertainties and inconsistencies in the educational data, leading to more accurate predictions of student outcomes. The decision makers and problem solver always seek to maximize the truth degree, minimize indeterminacy and falsity degree. Then, we usually consider truth degree $T_N = 1$, the indeterminacy and falsity degree $I_N = F_N = 0$, as follows $(1, 0, 0)$ for each trapezoidal neutrosophic number and this called the confirmation degree of each trapezoidal neutrosophic number (Abdel-Basset et al., 2019).

3.2. Some deep learning methods

In this subsection, we shall restrict our discussions to high-performance DNN methods, CNN methods as well as real-time RNN predictors, LSTM architecture, and Transformer methods.

Deep neural network (DNN) models, originally inspired by neurobiology, consist of multiple hidden layers (fully connected) that handle multiple inputs [10]. DNNs can model complex non-linear relationships [37]. DNN models have been applied to various fields, including image recognition, speech recognition, and natural language processing. However, in educational research, there are only a few applications of DNN so far, and the use of DNN in the analysis of student learning data is still in its early stages, particularly in predicting learning outcomes.

A convolutional neural network (CNN) is composed of a set of convolutional layers that employ nonlinear activation functions such as ReLU and tanh to activate weights in nodes. As the data passes through each layer, it generates increasingly

abstract features for the subsequent layers. CNNs excel in image processing applications, but have yet to be widely applied to the task of predicting student learning outcomes in educational data.

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) are a unique type of neural networks that possess internal self-connections, and can be used to model nonlinear dynamical systems with high accuracy [47]. RNNs have been utilized in various applications where temporal dependencies in the data are essential in designing the model. When processing sequential data, RNNs execute the same computations on each element of the input sequence, and its output at each step depends on previous inputs and computations. This ability allows the network to capture the history of past events by storing them in its hidden state variables. RNNs have been used for the dropout problem [14]. Long short-term memory (LSTM) is a popular variant of RNN that has gained significant attention due to its ability to store information for long periods of time. LSTM was introduced by [23] and has since been widely used in many works. LSTM is an improved form of RNN that overcomes the problem of vanishing gradients. This is achieved through memory cells aided by gates, which enable LSTM to learn long-term dependencies. Recent studies have shown that LSTM is effective in various applications, such as natural language processing and speech recognition.

The Transformer model can model observational data. Using embedding as a proxy, this approach can model the state variables and the phase space of the system. In this paper, we use the Transformer model with Encoder using Attention transformation, combining convolution; combining some layers of full connects, Dropout, and Decoder with Pooling to create a connection with the number of dimensions in the Unit. The application of node reduction techniques to predict student learning outcomes is consistent with previous models.

The idea of combining neutrosophics in deep learning models has also been proposed by some authors. For example, in the work [46], the authors used the neutrosophy approach in some extended models of LSTM and Transformer for the problem of sentiment analysis, and demonstrated the potential and effectiveness of this combined method. This idea is also proceeded by us in this paper for five introduced deep learning models. Each model was utilized to process the educational data and make predictions based on their respective strengths and capabilities. The results of this study showed that the proposed models outperformed deterministic models in terms of RMSE, MAE, and R2 metrics.

4. Deep learning model combined with neutrosophic theory

4.1. Problem

In this paper, we focus on task predictions based on historical data. Let X be a non-empty set. $X = X_1 \otimes X_2 \otimes \dots \otimes X_T, T \geq 1$. Each element of X has the form $x =$

$(x_1; x_2; \dots; x_T)$. We assume $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_T\}$ are available so that the prediction x_{T+q} where q is the desirable horizon ahead of the current timestamp. In the same way, to predict the value of the next timestamp x_{T+q+1} and $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_T, x_{T+1}\}$ are available. We hence formulate the input matrix at timestamp T as $X_T = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_T\}$. The prediction horizon is typically chosen to match the environmental requirements.

4.2. Methods

In this section, we introduce the combination of neutrosophic theory with some deep learning models to predict the next term grade. The overall model is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. General model

In many practical problems, data that is uncertain, unknown, and inconsistent exists [11,58]. For example, student scores, especially oral scores, in the process of teachers scoring students' scores, always have some uncertain, indeterminate, and inconsistent properties. Current research has not paid much attention or has only partially resolved the uncertainty, indeterminacy, and inconsistency in educational data in general, the problem of predicting student learning outcomes in particular.

Therefore, within the scope of this article, we propose a model that combines neutrosophic theory and some popular neural networks to improve performance in predicting student learning outcomes.

Figure 1 shows the general neutrosophic neural network architecture (DNN, CNN, RNN, LSTM, and Transformer). The proposed model is a combination of neutrosophic theory and some popular neural networks to improve the performance of the student learning outcomes predicted. Within the scope of the article to evaluate the performance of combining neutrosophic theory and neural networks to solve the problem of predicting students' scores, we used 05 popular neural networks DNN, CNN, RNN, LSMT, and Transformer. Some details of the neural network layers have been concrete shown in the section 5 (Results section). Detailed information about the layers of each network has been shown in the experimental section. Experimental results have shown that the proposed hybrid model gives better results than traditional models in predicting student outcomes.

For ease of comparison, in all models, we use the Adams optimization algorithm. The process of applying modern deep learning techniques to predict the learning outcomes of learners is conducted as follows:

Step 1: Model Construction.

The model architecture consists of the following primary layers:

Input Layer: Responsible for preprocessing raw data, including data cleaning, transformation into a neural-compatible format, and arrangement along a continuous temporal axis. The processed data is then forwarded to the encoder layer.

Encoder Layer: Transforms the input data based on neutrosophic theory. Specifically, the data is neutrosophicized using functions such as triangular, trapezoidal, or Gaussian membership functions to model uncertainty, indeterminacy, and inconsistency within the dataset (see Section 3.2 for details on fuzzy functions).

Hidden Layers: Employs conventional deep learning architectures, including DNN, CNN, RNN, LSTM, and Transformer, to process neutrosophicized data. Key considerations in this stage include input parameter selection, comprehensive data preprocessing (including neutrosophic transformation), and the construction of a continuous time scale.

Initially, the dataset is analyzed using a DNN model to establish a comparative baseline for other architectures. Subsequently, an RNN is proposed to incorporate temporal dynamics represented through students' semester-wise academic progression. Raw data is transformed into structured time series reflecting actual semester records. Neutrosophic-based models utilize specific transformation functions to convert inputs into neutrosophic sets. LSTM and Transformer models are also employed to generate alternative predictions using the same input dataset. Standard activation functions (e.g., sigmoid, tanh) are applied during training, alongside parameters such as batch size and number of epochs. The central focus is on adapting input data appropriately for each model and selecting optimal parameters to enhance learning efficiency.

Decoder and Output Layers: Outputs from hidden layers, expressed as neutrosophic values, are defuzzified to yield real-valued results. The final prediction layer synthesizes learned features to generate the model's output. Tables 2-6 show

detailed information about the layers of 5 models.

Table 2: DNN's sequential architecture

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 18)	0
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 18)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 128)	2432
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 128)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 1)	129

Table 3: CNN's sequential architecture

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
conv1d (Conv1D)	(None, 1, 64)	1216
max_pooling1d (MaxPooling1D)	(None, 1, 64)	0
conv1d_1 (Conv1D)	(None, 1, 64)	4160
max_pooling1d_1 (MaxPooling1D)	(None, 1, 64)	0
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 64)	0
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 64)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 128)	8320
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 128)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 1)	129

Table 4: RNN's sequential architecture

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
simple_rnn (SimpleRNN)	(None, 1, 312)	103272
simple_rnn_1 (SimpleRNN)	(None, 1, 56)	20664
simple_rnn_2 (SimpleRNN)	(None, 1, 88)	12760
simple_rnn_3 (SimpleRNN)	(None, 1, 504)	298872
simple_rnn_4 (SimpleRNN)	(None, 264)	203016
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 264)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 1)	265

Table 5: LSTM's sequential architecture

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
lstm (LSTM)	(None, 1, 128)	75264
lstm_1 (LSTM)	(None, 64)	49408

flatten (Flatten)	(None, 64)	0
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 64)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 128)	8320
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 128)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 1)	129

Table 6: TRANSFORMER's sequential architecture

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
input_1 (InputLayer)	[(None, 1, 18)]	0
layer_normalization (LayerNormalization)	(LayerNorma (None, 1, 18)	36
multi_head_attention (MultiHeadAttention)	(None, 1, 18)	0
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 1, 504)	298872
layer_normalization_1 (LayerNormalization)	(None, 1, 18)	36
conv1d (Conv1D)	(None, 1, 4)	76
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 1, 4)	0
conv1d_1 (Conv1D)	(None, 1, 18)	90
layer_normalization_2 (LayerNormalization)	(None, 1, 18)	36
multi_head_attention_1 (MultiHeadAttention)	(None, 1, 18)	76818
dropout_2(Dropout)	(None, 1, 18)	0
layer_normalization_3 (LayerNormalization)	(None, 1, 18)	36
conv1d_2 (Conv1D)	(None, 1, 4)	76
dropout_3 (Dropout)	(None, 1, 4)	0
conv1d_3 (Conv1D)	(None, 1, 18)	90
layer_normalization_4 (LayerNormal (None, 1, 18)	(LayerNor (None, 1, 18)	36
multi_head_attention_2 (MultiHeadAttention)	(None, 1, 18)	76818
dropout_4 (Dropout)	(None, 1, 18)	0
layer_normalization_5 (LayerNormalization)	(None, 1, 18)	36
conv1d_4 (Conv1D)	(None, 1, 4)	76
global_average_pooling1d (GlobalAveragePooling1D)	(None, 1)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 128)	256

dropout_8 (Dropout)	(None, 128)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 1)	129

Step 2. Model Learning. The principle of this step is to calculate the weights, and to handle the optimization problem. In which the parameters (weight w , bias - bias of each node) will be machine learned to suggest the most optimal results. In this paper, we deal with the back-propagation problem with the Adam optimizer algorithm and use MAE in the process of learning the model. In this paper the parameters of the model are introduced in Table 7.

Table 7: The parameters of the models

Hyper-parameters	Selection
Learning rate α	0.0003
Drop-out rate	0.3
Number of epochs	1000
Loss function	Mean absolute error
Optimizer	Adam

Step 3. Prediction and Evaluation:

After estimating model parameters in Step 2, the test data are input to evaluate performance using RMSE, MAE, and R^2 . RMSE, the root of mean squared errors, serves as the primary aggregation metric, while MAE and R^2 assess average error magnitude and model fit, respectively.

In sum, this study applies modern deep learning models (DNN, CNN, RNN, LSTM, Transformer) with tuned parameters and neutrosophic set-based preprocessing. Input data, extracted from structured Excel files, are fed into the models for training and evaluation. Once trained, the models predict outcomes using prior data, with accuracy visualized in Section 5 based on experimental data from Hanoi Metropolitan University.

4.3. Computational Complexity Analysis

The computational complexity of Algorithm 1 is primarily influenced by three core components: the neutrosophic encoding stage, the model construction and training phase, and the evaluation step.

Algorithm 1. Neutrosophic Deep Learning for Student Performance Prediction

- 1 **Input:** X is Historical student records; H is Prediction horizon;
- 2 F_n : Neutrosophic membership functions;
- 3 Model \in {DNN, CNN, RNN, LSTM, Transformer};
- 4 Hyperparameters: learning rate η , dropout rate d , epochs E
- 5 **Output:** \hat{y} Predicted student performance score
- 6 Preprocess the raw student data: clean, normalize, order by time
- 7 **For** each input $x_i \in X$ **do**
- 8 Encode x_i using neutrosophic trapezoidal function:

```

9           [T(xi), I(xi), F(xi)] ← Fn()
10  end for
11  Construct model with:
12     Input layer (neutrosophic vector)
13     Encoder (neutrosophic transformation)
14     Hidden layers based on selected model
15     Decoder (neutrosophic defuzzification)
16     Output layer (regression head)
17  Train the model using Adam optimizer with MAE loss
18  Run training for E epochs on training data
19  Evaluate model on test data using RMSE, MAE, R2
20  Return  $\hat{y}$ 

```

(1) Neutrosophic Encoding

For each student record $x_i \in X$, the algorithm computes a triplet $[T(x_i), I(x_i), F(x_i)]$ using neutrosophic trapezoidal membership functions. Assuming $|X| = n$ and that each function evaluation takes constant time $O(1)$, the total time complexity for this step is $O(n)$.

(2) Model Construction and Training

Let M denote the number of model parameters, E the number of training epochs, and B the mini-batch size. The forward and backward passes through the deep learning model (e.g., DNN, CNN, RNN, LSTM, or Transformer) typically require $O(M)$ operations per sample. Thus, the training complexity is approximately $O(E \cdot \frac{n}{B} \cdot M)$, assuming that each epoch processes all n training samples. In the case of Transformer models, which are known to have quadratic attention mechanisms, the worst-case complexity increases to $O(E \cdot \frac{n}{B} \cdot L \cdot d^2)$, where L is the number of layers and d is the dimensionality of the hidden representations.

(3) Evaluation Phase

Once training is complete, the model is evaluated on a test set of size n' . Each prediction requires a single forward pass, resulting in a complexity of $O(n' \cdot M)$.

Overall Complexity

The dominant factor in the computational complexity stems from the model training phase. The total complexity can be approximated as:

$$O(n) + O\left(E \cdot \frac{n}{B} \cdot M\right) + O(n' \cdot M)$$

which simplifies to: $O(E \cdot \frac{n}{B} \cdot M)$, under the assumption that $n' \ll n$ and $M \gg 1$. This formulation provides a practical upper bound for estimating resource demands, particularly in large-scale educational datasets.

5. Experiments

5.1. Dataset

The data used in this study is reality training data collected from Hanoi Metropolitan University, which is the public university directly under the People's Committee of Hanoi, Vietnam. Every year, the training management department has statistical data on the results of the subjects of the students of the majors in the university. The Faculties, the Training Management Department, and Student Affairs Department keep track of students' scores, evaluate and are responsible for advising the Board of Directors on information about students, lecturers, and policies that manages and supports the students. In addition, the functional Departments and the Training Management Department need to have an overall objective assessment of the student's learning status to propose solutions to support the learning process, give early warnings to students with alarmingly low academic results; and at the same time, make plans with a team of academic advisors to closely follow, help and improve students' learning results. If there are early predictions about learners' learning outcomes, the Faculties and functional Departments can make judgments about the direction of students' learning quality, using it to adjust the training plan and propose policies to support students to achieve the best educational results.

Study score data provided by Faculty, Department of Training Management. Other data was collected from various sources from the Student Affairs Department, from lecturers, students, and students' family members, through data collection surveys (online and offline), ... All data including student management status (tuition fees, personal information,...); entrance exam scores, foreign language scores, informatics scores, and subject scores of students are divided into enrollment data and training data for 8 semesters; according to 4 years of study. The student's scores are divided into number scores (on a 10-point scale and a 4-point scale) and the letter score, which are displayed in detail with the specific number of credits for the modules. The letter score convention and score conversion are detailed in Table 8.

Table 8: Letter point convention and point conversion

Ranking by letter score	10-point score	4-point score
A ⁺	[9,5;10]	4,0
A	[8,5;9,5)	3,7
B ⁺	[8,0;8,5)	3,5
B	[7,0;8,0)	3,0
C ⁺	[6,5;7,0)	2,5
C	[5,5;6,5)	2,0
D ⁺	[5,0;5,5)	1,5
D	[4,0;4,9)	1,0

F	[0,0;4,0)	0,0
---	-----------	-----

Data were collected from official student score data sources, with strict regulations on the form of training. Specifically: teaching activities are carried out at school, but practical activities, internships, practical experiences, and online teaching can be done outside of school.; the time to organize teaching activities is from 6 a.m. to 8 p.m. on weekdays from Monday to Saturday. At the beginning of the school year, the training plan is publicly announced. The school year plan shows the main milestones of training activities in the school year for all forms and training programs and is promptly announced to lecturers and students before the start of the school year. A school year has 3 main semesters with a total of at least 30 weeks of class. In addition to the main semester, the School may organize additional semesters.

At the beginning of each course, students can access the LMS to sign up for their 4-year study plan. Before each semester, students log into LMS a few weeks ahead to register for the course and the number of credits they will accumulate (expected to) during that semester. Before the start of each semester, students must register to study on the University's academic registration system. Students must register for classes of the courses they intend to study in the semester, including new courses, some failed courses (for retaking), and some passed courses (to improve grades, if desired) based on the list of open courses and the registration conditions of each course. For students with normal academic performance, the number of academic credits that students must register in each semester is at least $2/3$, up to $3/2$ the average number of credits of a semester according to the total number of credits of the training program that the student attends (excluding the last semester of the course). For students with weak academic performance in the previous semester, in the next semester, students can only register for a maximum number of credits equal to the average number of credits of a semester according to the total number of credits of the training program in which the student is registered (excluding the last semester of the course). There is no set minimum and maximum amount of credit for students when registering to study in the extra semester. For each module, students are assessed through at least 01 component point/credit of the theory course; 02 component points/practice course credits. Component scores are rated on a 0-10 scale. The assessment method, assessment form, number of sub-points, and weight of each sub-point are specified in the detailed outline of each module. Normally, the grade will be assigned to 10% attendance, 30% for midterm assessment, and 60% for final assessment. For internships and professional practice courses held outside of school, students are assessed regularly during their study, at least 01 component point/credit.

Students' learning results are valuated after each semester or after each school year, based on the results of the modules within the requirements of the training program that the student have studied. The average score of the modules that the student has studied in a semester (semester average), in a school year (academic year average), or

calculated from the beginning of the course (cumulative grade point average) is calculated according to the official grade of the course with the weight being the number of credits for that course. Students are graded according to their semester average, year point average or cumulative grade point average. According to a 4-point scale: From 3.6 to 4.0: Excellent; From 3.2 to under 3.6: Very Good; From 2.5 to under 3.2: Good; From 2.0 to less than 2.5: Fair; from 1.0 to less than 2.0: Poor and less than 1.0: Very Poor. On a 10-point scale: From 9.0 to 10.0: Excellent; From 8.0 to less than 9.0: Very Good; From 7.0 to less than 8.0: Good; From 5.0 to less than 7.0: Fair; From 4.0 to less than 5.0: Poor and Under 4.0: Very Poor, see Table 9.

Table 9. Sorting students by cumulative grade point average

Ranking	10-point score	4-point score
Excellent	[9,0;10]	[3,6-4,0]
Very Good	[8,0;9,0)	[3,2-3,6)
Good	[7,0-8,0)	[2,5;3,2)
Fair	[5,0;7,0]	[2,0;2,5)
Poor	[4,0;5,0)	[1,0;2,0)
Very Poor	[0;4,0)	[0;1,0)

In this paper, to capture and represent the uncertainties and indeterminacies present in the educational data, we incorporate neutrosophic logic and uncertainty theory into the models. This approach acknowledges that educational data can contain ambiguous and inaccurate information due to factors such as conversion methods, assessment difficulty, learning methods, and psychological states of students. Neutrosophic functions are up to 6 neutrosophic sets: Excellent, Very Good, Good, Fair, Poor, and Very Poor. We use the trapezoidal function to neutrosophic with the general formula $[a, b, c, d; 1, 0, 0], a \leq b \leq c \leq d (T_N = 1, I_N = 0, F_N = 0)$. Details of the values corresponding to the neutrosophic set are, for example, Very Poor = $[0, 0.2, 3.7, 4.1; 1, 0, 0]$; Poor = $[3.8, 4.2, 4.7, 5.1; 1, 0, 0]$; Fair = $[4.8, 5.2, 5.7, 7.1; 1, 0, 0]$; Good = $[6.8, 7.2, 7.7, 8.1; 1, 0, 0]$; Very Good = $[7.8, 8.2, 8.7, 9.1; 1, 0, 0]$ and Excellent = $[8.8, 9.2, 9.7, 10.0; 1, 0, 0]$. And concretely, for example, the neutrosophic functions are

$$T_{Very\ Poor}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq 0, x > 4.1 \\ x/0.2 & \text{if } 0 < x \leq 0.2 \\ 1 & \text{if } 0.2 < x \leq 3.7 \\ 4.1 - x/0.4 & \text{if } 3.7 < x \leq 4.1 \end{cases}$$

$$I_{Very\ Poor}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \leq 0, x > 4.1 \\ 0.2 - x/0.2 & \text{if } 0 < x \leq 0.2 \\ 0 & \text{if } 0.2 < x \leq 3.7 \\ x - 3.7/0.4 & \text{if } 3.7 < x \leq 4.1 \end{cases}$$

$$F_{Very\ Poor}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \leq 0, x > 4.1 \\ 0.2 - x / 0.2 & \text{if } 0 < x \leq 0.2 \\ 0 & \text{if } 0.2 < x \leq 3.7 \\ x - 3.7 / 0.4 & \text{if } 3.7 < x \leq 4.1 \end{cases}$$

The HNMU applies a uniform credit-based training method for all courses and forms of training. The credit-based training method is a method of organizing training for each course, allowing students to accumulate credits for each module and implement a training program according to their individual study plan and with the school curriculum. To build a student data set and process the data set into appropriate matrix arrays, we have surveyed and collected 2613 observed data of students in Primary Education, Early childhood Education majors of HNMU, courses from 2014 to 2021. Specific subjects (e.g. Primary Education) are provided in Table A-1, Appendix A. The dataset is divided into 933 full data samples, each data sample is represented by 1 row. Data were cleaned, and unnecessary attributes (variables) and variables that were not evaluated in this study were removed. Using the technique of dimensionality reduction, we remove subjects with few enrollments to optimize the data set, fill in the information and systematize the subjects in each semester. In this dataset, we have removed some data on physical or gifted-related subjects, and financial-related attributes of students. Also attributes with too little data, or with a lot of empty data are also removed (mainly fall into the data of scores of electives that few students choose). We also focused on the score data (scale of 10) and omitted the letter score data and the score data (scale of 4). From a dataset consisting of 2613 samples with 85 attribute variables, deployed to 933 cleaned data. The data was redistributed by time scale, sorted by semesters, and 448 data samples were used for training and testing. The student's score distribution is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Distribution of student's grade

5.2. Case Study and Parameters

In this paper, we present three case studies of student data to illustrate the proposed method.

Case 1: Predict the learning outcomes of the n th semester if the learning outcome of the $n-1$ semester is given. That is, knowing the value of x_{n-1} , predict the value of x_n , $1 < n \leq m$, see Figure 3.

Figure 3. Prediction framework for Case 1

Case 2: Predict the student's n th term learning results when the learning results of the previous 2 semesters are given. That is, knowing the values of x_{n-2} , x_{n-1} , predict the value of x_n , $2 < n \leq m$, see Figure 4.

Figure 4. Prediction framework for Case 2

Case 3: Predict the student's n th semester learning results when knowing the learning results of the previous 3 semesters. That is, knowing the value of x_{n-3} , x_{n-2} , x_{n-1} , predict the value of x_n , $3 < n \leq m$, see Figure 5.

Figure 5. Prediction framework for Case 3

With the obtained raw dataset, the first comment shows that the score spectrum focuses on two levels of rating: Very Good and Good. In addition, the first-year students' academic results are often poor when compared with the students' actual desires and capabilities. By the second year, when students are familiar with the teaching and learning methods at the school, the results are closer to their ability. From semester 4 onwards, when they get used to the new learning environment and have clear learning goals, the student's learning results are relatively stable and clearly differentiated among the subjects (Excellent, Very Good, Good, Fair, Poor and Very Poor).

To search for predictions with optimal results, we introduce into the model some neutrosophic functions to neutrosophy the data. In this paper, we use neutrosophic function to 6 neutrosophic sets: Very Poor, Poor, Fair, Good, Very Good, Excellent. The detailed values corresponding to the neutrosophic set include: Very Poor = $[0, 0.2, 3.7, 4.1; 1, 0, 0]$; Poor = $[3.8, 4.2, 4.7, 5.1; 1, 0, 0]$; Fair = $[4.8, 5.2, 5.7, 7.1; 1, 0, 0]$; Good = $[6.8, 7.2, 7.7, 8.1; 1, 0, 0]$; Very Good = $[7.8, 8.2, 8.7, 9.1; 1, 0, 0]$ and Excellent = $[8.8, 9.2,$

9.7, 10.0;1,0,0]. Figure 6 show the membership functions of “Very Poor” neutrosophic number.

Figure 6. Neutrosophic membership functions

To solve the problem of predicting student learning outcomes through time series, component transcripts are divided into semesters. The duration of each semester is 5 months, so each transcript is divided into different semesters and for each semester, the student's score is sorted and calculated uniformly.

The data is divided into training and testing subsets. The training set consists of 70% of the randomly selected original data set, and the test set consists of the remaining 30%.

The first scenario we set up is to use the results of one semester to predict the learning results of the next semester. The second scenario is to use the results of the two semesters to predict the results of the third semester. The third scenario is to use the results of the three semesters to predict the results of the fourth semester.

The models used take into account the time factor, multi-event (each subject is 1 event), and neutrosophic set integration to input data, combined with time series built on the data set to predict the outcome of a semester after knowing the results of the previous semester.

In general, the training dataset of student learning outcomes is not linearly separable, so that the linear regression or PLA method are inefficient. Since the problem of predicting learning outcomes is a multi-classification problem, logistic regression with the sigmoid function is ineffective. Therefore, modern deep learning models, especially those well adapted to time series, are proposed to process this type of data. The deep learning methods used for data analysis include classical DNN, CNN, RNN,

LSTM, and Transformer methods. Finally, we use the parameters of the models, specifically as in Table 10.

Table 10: The parameters of the models

Hyper-parameters	Selection
Learning rate α	0.0003
Drop-out rate	0.3
Number of epochs	1000
Loss function	Mean absolute error
Optimizer	Adam

5.3. Experimental Results

Evaluative Metrics: The Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and R2-score to estimate the performance and the difference between the student's actual GPA and predicted GPA, allowing for appropriate model selection based on the situation. In reality, the lower the RMSE and MAE, the better the model and its predictions, and the higher the R2-score, the better the model and its suitability.

Table 11 shows results of neutrosophy deep learning models. The architecture of the five models is detailed in the tables 2-6. The average errors are evaluated 10 times on the 10 folds corresponding to Cases 1, 2 and 3. When combining neutrosophic functions to fuzzify input data, calibrating parameters of applied deep learning algorithms, with the training data sample accounting for 70% and 30% of the data used for testing, we get the predicted results as shown in Figures 7, 8 and 9 (for 01 test). The test is divided into different cases: (Case 1) Using the previous semester's average data to predict the next semester's average score; (Case 2) Using the average data of the 2 previous semesters to predict the average score of the third semester; (Case 3) Using the average data of the 3 previous semesters to predict the average score of the fourth semester.

Table 11: Average error for Case 1, 2, 3 with Neutrosophic Approach

Method /Metric	RMSE			MAE			R2(%)		
	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3
DNN	0.89 ± 0.09	0.57 ± 0.05	0.87 ± 0.05	0.75± 0.06	0.47 ± 0.05	0.74 ± 0.04	12.76 ± 4.90	48.42 ± 5.74	59.45 ± 4.00
CNN	0.90± 0.07	0.58 ± 0.04	0.80 ± 0.08	0.74± 0.04	0.46 ± 0.02	0.62 ± 0.07	11.40 ± 5.06	47.03 ± 5.80	62.04 ± 5.36
RNN	0.92 ± 0.07	0.60 ± 0.05	0.80 ± 0.08	0.73 ± 0.04	0.45 ± 0.03	0.60± 0.06	12.39 ± 6.06	46.16 ± 6.82	62.14 ± 7.67
LSTM	0.91 ± 0.07	0.57 ± 0.04	0.76 ± 0.11	0.74 ± 0.04	0.45 ± 0.03	0.59 ± 0.07	12.73 ± 4.97	49.51 ± 5.40	65.28 ± 8.93
Transformer	0.89 ± 0.08	0.59 ± 0.06	0.79 ± 0.06	0.74 ± 0.04	0.47 ± 0.06	0.59 ± 0.05	13.13 ± 7.65	45.54 ± 8.92	65.95 ± 4.33

Figure 7: Graph of Prediction (neutrosophic data, Case 1)

Figure 8: Graph of Prediction (neutrosophic data, Case 2)

Figure 9. Graph of Prediction (neutrosophic data, Case 3)

For Case 1: Using the previous semester's average data to predict the next semester's average score, we estimate the errors (average after 10 tests) of the algorithms as shown in Table 11. In this case we can see that the R2 metrics of all five

methods are so slow, we do not recommend using this case for real-world forecasting problems.

For Case 2: Using the average data of the 2 previous semesters to predict the average score of the third semester, we get the predicted results as shown in Figure 8 (for 01 test) and the errors (average after 10 tests) of the algorithms in Table 11. In this Case, we can see that the quality of forecasting methods increases significantly compared to Case 1. In this case the R2 metrics of all five method are approximately 50% for neutrosophic cases, so in cases where much information is not collected, we can also use this model for the problem of predicting student scores.

For Case 3: we use the grade data of the previous three semesters to forecast the academic performance for the fourth semester's grades. From the comparison table below we see that in the case of using the Neutrosophic approach, all metrics are improved compared to the case without using the neutrosophic approach. Especially, we see that for the DNN method, the differences are significantly improved compared to other methods. Moreover, from Table 11 we can see that, in the case of using the neutrosophic approach, the R2-score parameter of all 5 methods is greater than 50%, which proves that all five methods are suitable for the data and the problem.

5.4. Comparison analysis and Discussion

In this section, the study compares the model that was proposed to traditional deep learning models employing real number, such as, DNN, CNN, RNN, LSTN and TRANSFORMER on the three metrics RMSE, MAE, and R2-score, which are designed to analyze the strengths and weaknesses of each method. The results will discuss on the performance and suitability of the proposed model based on the educational data procured from HNMU and will provide recommendations regarding its application. Comparison results estimate the errors (average after 10 tests) of the algorithms as shown in Table 12. From the results are presented in Table 12, we conclude that the numerical results that are highlighted in “bold” indicate that the corresponding forecasting method has better results than the other method.

Figures 10, 11, and 12 compare the errors of five deep learning methods using the neutrosophic approach for Case 1, Case 2, and Case 3, respectively. From the Figure 10, we find that the R2 metrics of all method are so slow. It is recommended that we should not use a prediction model in this Case 1. Figure 11 shows that the performance distinction of the neutrosophic approach compared to the real case is not clear. Note that in this case the R2-score has improved compared to case 1, but it has not reached 50%. In case of Figure12, we can see that in general, the Neutrosophy RNN, LSTM and Transformer methods have similar and better performance than the other methods.

Table 12: Average error comparison for Case 1, 2, 3

Method /Metric		RMSE		MAE		R2 (%)	
		Real input	Neuro. Approach	Real input	Neuro. Approach	Real input	Neuro. Approach
Case 1	DNN	1.06 ± 0.33	0.89 ± 0.09	1.07 ± 0.11	0.75 ± 0.06	48.26 ± 32.00	12.76 ± 4.90
	CNN	0.92 ± 0.06	0.90 ± 0.07	0.73 ± 0.04	0.74 ± 0.04	8.52 ± 4.65	11.40 ± 5.06
	RNN	0.89 ± 0.05	0.92 ± 0.07	0.72 ± 0.04	0.73 ± 0.04	12.6 ± 8.49	12.39 ± 6.06
	LSTM	0.90 ± 0.05	0.91 ± 0.07	0.74 ± 0.03	0.74 ± 0.04	9.72 ± 5.39	12.73 ± 4.97
	Transformer	0.90 ± 0.04	0.89 ± 0.08	0.74 ± 0.03	0.74 ± 0.04	± 5.40	13.13 ± 7.65
Case 2	DNN	1.10 ± 0.11	0.57 ± 0.05	1.13 ± 0.12	0.47 ± 0.05	186.07 ± 119.20	48.42 ± 5.74
	CNN	0.53 ± 0.05	0.58 ± 0.04	0.41 ± 0.03	0.46 ± 0.02	46.39 ± 6.51	47.03 ± 5.80
	RNN	0.55 ± 0.07	0.60 ± 0.05	0.42 ± 0.05	0.45 ± 0.03	37.12 ± 18.19	46.16 ± 6.82
	LSTM	0.52 ± 0.04	0.57 ± 0.04	0.40 ± 0.03	0.45 ± 0.03	52.42 ± 9.95	49.51 ± 5.40
	Transformer	0.63 ± 0.07	0.59 ± 0.06	0.48 ± 0.04	0.47 ± 0.06	26.83 ± 5.96	45.54 ± 8.92
Case 3	DNN	2.44 ± 0.16	0.87 ± 0.05	2.31 ± 0.16	0.74 ± 0.04	-211.39 ± 75.45	59.45 ± 4.00
	CNN	0.86 ± 0.08	0.80 ± 0.08	0.67 ± 0.07	0.62 ± 0.07	59.01 ± 7.00	62.04 ± 5.36
	RNN	0.82 ± 0.13	0.80 ± 0.08	0.62 ± 0.12	0.60 ± 0.06	60.69 ± 9.20	62.14 ± 7.67
	LSTM	0.88 ± 0.13	0.76 ± 0.11	0.71 ± 0.15	0.59 ± 0.07	58.51 ± 11.54	65.28 ± 8.93
	Transformer	0.93 ± 0.07	0.79 ± 0.06	0.77 ± 0.06	0.59 ± 0.05	53.05 ± 7.60	65.95 ± 4.33

Tables 12 present the average error comparison of implementing traditional deep learning models for predicting student outcomes. It seems that, RNN, LSTM, and Transformer methods significantly outperform the other methods, confirming the effectiveness of our approach as we achieved consistent results on the validation set.

Figure 10. Compare the errors of five deep learning methods using neutrosophic approach – Case 1

Figure 11. Compare the errors of five deep learning methods using neutrosophic approach – Case 2

Figure 12. Compare the errors of five deep learning methods using neutrosophic approach – Case 3

In Case 3, the RNN, LSTM, or Transformer model used in this study give better results than other methods. While our research idea and implementation can follow a university's grading system, other classification systems may require different implementations. Therefore, we will make recommendations to use the model in this case for practical application at HNMU.

Similar studies have been described in the literature, including monitoring and evaluating student learning outcomes, comparative research on artificial neural networks, and statistical models to predict student averages. However, our approach differs in considering the time factor, semester differences, and the use of neutrosophic functions for input data fuzzification.

Three case studies of data from Hanoi Metropolitan University showed that the proposed approach outperformed traditional neural network approaches when working with real numbers.

6. Conclusions

The field of artificial intelligence and machine learning has seen significant advancements in recent years with the emergence of DL models. DL's ability to handle large datasets has also led to its widespread applications in different fields, including educational data science. The study presents experimental results for five prediction models, with a focus on constructing datasets and applying DL models to predict student outcomes. In the context of predicting student outcomes, neutrosophy is used to handle the inherent uncertainties and inconsistencies in educational data. The aim of this research is to improve the higher education system by predicting students' success and providing additional assessments to enhance the education system's development. By predicting a student's result through internal assessment, lecturers can devote extra time to help improve their final examination marks. The model can also be used to identify at-risk students and provide them with warnings and support to improve their performance.

One potential challenge could be the availability and quality of the data used for training and testing the models. The study used data from the Hanoi Metropolitan University, and it is possible that the data may not be representative of other educational institutions or contexts. Additionally, the quality of the data, such as missing values or outliers, could affect the performance of the models. Another potential challenge could be the complexity and interpretability of the deep learning models used in the framework. Deep learning models are known for their black-box nature, which makes it difficult to understand how they arrive at their predictions. This could be a limitation in educational management decision-making, where transparency and interpretability are important. All these limitations give chances to potential future directions of the proposed framework for widening various data used for training and testing the models.

Compliance with Ethical Standards:

Contributions

All authors contributed equally.

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Ethics declarations

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Ethical approval

This article does not contain any studies with human or animal subjects.

Informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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Appendix A

Table A. Variables used in data analysis

Semester	Course Code	Course name
0	M1	Subject 1 (Math)
0	M2	Subject 2 (Literature)
0	M3	Subject 3 (English)
0	TD	Total score for admission
1	20TRA002	Defense and Security education 1
1	20TRA003	Basic Principles of Marxism-Leninism 1
1	30PRI002	Practice Vietnamese language skills in elementary school
1	30PRI003	Literature and teaching literary works in elementary education
1	30PRI072	Art activities at primary education
1	30PRI073	Practice Vietnamese skills
1	30PRI120	Mathematical foundations 1
1	30PRI301	Art Education at primary education
1	30TRA002	General law
1	30TRA045	Physical Education 1
1	30TRA054	Psychology
1	30TRA121	Marxist-Leninist philosophy
1	30TRA126	Defense and Security education 1
1	TA1	English (entrance)
2	20TRA004	Information technology
2	20TRA006	Defense and Security education 2
2	20TRA007	English 1
2	20TRA008	Basic Principles of Marxism-Leninism 2
2	20TRA013	Logic
2	20TRA026	Cultivate teacher qualities
2	30PRI004	Algebra Foundation in elementary school
2	30PRI006	Physiology of elementary school children
2	30PRI074	Literature
2	30TRA001	State administrative management and industry management
2	30TRA023	English
2	30TRA024	Chinese
2	30TRA025	Korean
2	30TRA031	Pedagogics
2	30TRA032	Pedagogic 1
2	30TRA110	Developing Information capacity in the digital age
2	30TRA122	Marxist-Leninist political economy
2	30TRA127	Defense and Security 2
2	30TRA128	Defense and Security 3
3	20TRA009	Study of Hanoi
3	20TRA010	Vietnamese Practice
3	20TRA011	Vietnamese cultural establishment
3	20TRA012	World Civilization History
3	20TRA014	Education for sustainable development
3	20TRA015	Environmental Population and drug prevention
3	20TRA016	Vietnam's seas and islands
3	20TRA017	Defense and Security 3
3	20TRA018	English 2
3	20TRA906	Statistical Mathematics
3	30CIV006	General economics
3	30CIV075	Problems of today's times
3	30PRI016	The natural and social basis

3	30PRI020	Vietnamese teaching techniques in primary education 1
3	30PRI049	Practice teaching skills
3	30PRI075	Mathematical foundations 2
3	30PRI079	Instructions for making traditional teaching materials
3	30PRI181	Psychology and primary school education 1
3	30PRI210	Moral Education in elementary school
3	30PRI257	Primary school headteacher training
3	30PRI303	Teaching aids in primary school
3	30TRA003	Physical Education 3
3	30TRA033	Pedagogic 2
3	30TRA039	Music Practice
3	30TRA040	Art Practice
3	30TRA046	Physical education 2
3	30TRA058	Personal Financial Management Skills 1
3	30TRA070	Scientific research method
3	30TRA080	Personal Financial Management Skills 2
3	30TRA111	Music and music perception
3	30TRA112	Art and artistic perception
3	30TRA123	Science socialism
3	30TRA129	Defense and Security 4
4	20TRA019	The Revolutionary Way of the Communist Party of Vietnam
4	20TRA031	Educating capacity building
4	20TRA040	Complimentary English
4	30PRI007	Vietnamese
4	30PRI009	Vietnamese teach techniques 1
4	30PRI021	Vietnamese teach techniques in primary education 2
4	30PRI023	Methods of teaching natural and social subjects 1
4	30PRI036	Studying history - geography in Hanoi for teaching in primary education
4	30PRI037	Semantics - pragmatics in teaching Vietnamese in primary education
4	30PRI041	Electronic keyboard and its application in primary education
4	30PRI055	Pedagogical internship 1
4	30PRI077	Primary School Math teaching techniques 1
4	30PRI078	Health and physical education in elementary school 1
4	30PRI080	Primary School Math teaching techniques 2
4	30PRI081	Application of Information and communication technology in primary education
4	30PRI082	Health and physical education in elementary school 2
4	30PRI190	Art and teaching art in primary school
4	30TRA034	Pedagogic 3
4	30TRA124	Ho Chi Minh Thought

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